

EXPERIENCES OF OVERSEAS FILIPINO WORKERS IN DIGITAL PARENTING

Rizal Technological University, December 2024

Researchers:

Danice L. Balla
Maica Adriana V. Francisco
Diana B. Lopez
Rhea Elizah B. Reyes
Amorsolo F. Espiritu

ABSTRACT

This qualitative study explores the experiences of Overseas Filipino Workers (OFWs) in digital parenting, focusing on how they maintain relationships with their children despite physical separation. Through in-depth semi-structured interviews with ten OFW parents, the research reveals that these parents prioritize their children's emotional well-being by fostering meaningful digital connections. The findings indicate that OFW parents are deeply concerned about their children's welfare, strive for consistent communication, and adapt to the complexities of being away. The study highlights the importance of technology in bridging emotional gaps and facilitating parental involvement from a distance. Ultimately, the research contributes to a deeper understanding of transnational parenting dynamics and the resilience of families navigating the challenges of separation.

Keywords: Overseas Filipino Workers, digital parenting, parent-child relationships, emotional well-being, transnational families.

Introduction

The phenomenon of Overseas Filipino Workers (OFWs) has become a defining aspect of Filipino society, with millions working abroad to provide for their families. This study investigates the unique challenges faced by OFW parents in maintaining relationships with their children through digital parenting practices. The research aims to explore how these parents navigate the emotional complexities of separation while utilizing technology to stay connected. The study is grounded in Family Systems Theory and Attachment Theory, which provide insights into the dynamics of parent-child relationships in the context of physical distance. The findings are expected to reveal the strategies employed by OFWs to foster emotional bonds and support their children's development despite the challenges posed by migration.

Methods

The study employs a qualitative research design, utilizing semi-structured interviews to gather in-depth insights from participants.

Respondents and Sampling

The respondents include ten OFW parents, either mothers or fathers, aged 30 years and above, who have been working overseas for at least four years. The participants were selected using a homogeneous purposive sampling technique to ensure relevance to the research objectives.

Research Instruments

The research instrument used was a semi-structured interview guide, which included open-ended questions designed to elicit detailed responses about the participants' experiences with digital parenting. The interviews aimed to explore themes related to communication, emotional support, and parenting strategies.

Data Gathering

Data gathering was conducted through virtual interviews via Google Meet and Messenger, allowing participants to share their experiences in a comfortable setting. The interviews lasted between 30 minutes to 1 hour, and participants were informed about the study's purpose and their rights.

Data Analysis

Thematic analysis was used to analyze the qualitative data collected from the online interviews. This method allowed for the identification of key themes and patterns related to the experiences of OFW parents in digital parenting.

Results

The results indicate that OFW parents utilize various digital tools to maintain communication and emotional support for their children. Key themes identified include efficient communication, maintaining parental support, time management, and prioritization of children's well-being. Participants collectively stated that technology has significantly improved their ability to connect with their children, despite the challenges of physical separation.

Furthermore, the results highlight the significance of taking into account not only the material contributions but also the emotional and psychological well-being of the children to address the challenges posed by parental migration, even in the face of distance and the availability of digital media as a substitute for communication. As stated by Siskind, D. G. and Helms, H. M. Economic globalization and labor flows have increased the prevalence of migrant worker families, or families with one or more family members residing in different countries for employment. With the growth of migrant worker families worldwide, the study of migrant work and family separation is important to the discussion of work and family science. Migration is often a stressful experience for workers, many are willing to accept and deal with the stressors they face in order to pursue financial security and earn a livelihood for themselves and their families.

Discussion

The study conclude how Overseas Filipino Workers (OFW) describe their experiences in digital parenting. They rely on effective communication through social media, video calls, and instant messaging to address their children's emotional needs. Beyond communication, these parents provide psychological, emotional, and financial support to ensure their children feel secure and valued. Time management is a significant challenge as they balance work schedules, time zones, and personal commitments to engage meaningfully. Their efforts emphasize the importance of their children's social, emotional, and academic development, underscoring the need for a work-life balance to remain emotionally present while fulfilling professional duties.

In view of parent-child relationships, the participants collectively shared their experiences through themes of emotional engagement, which emphasizes the value of consistent care and communication; barriers and adaptability, which reflect the difficulties of time differences, work demands, and financial constraints; and dependability, where parents prioritize being dependable sources of emotional and financial support. The study also examined the perspectives of OFW parents on parent-child relationships.

Last but not least, the study explored how OFW parents made adjustments with the particular difficulties of parenting from a distance by using time management techniques, strategic communication and interaction, unwavering parental commitment, and a sense of adaptation and acceptance. Together, these observations highlight the fortitude, commitment, and inventiveness of OFW parents in sustaining close relationships, guaranteeing the stability of their children, and negotiating the challenges of long-distance parenting. This study findings highlighted the importance of parental connectedness and maintaining the relationship with their children. Being a part of something bigger than oneself was defined as connectedness. It was an accompaniment, or a sensation of belonging (Montajes, 2023)

References

Siskind, D. G. & Helms, H. M. (2020). Migrant work and its impact on parents, children, and partners. In Stephen Sweet (Ed.) Work and Family Encyclopedia. Work and Family Researchers Network. Retrieve from, <https://wfrn.org/encyclopedia/migrant-work-and-its-impact-on-parents-children-and-partners/>

Montajes G. (2023). Parental relationships of overseas Filipino parents and their parental bonding | Excellencia: International multi-disciplinary Journal of education (2994-9521). Multi Journals Press. <https://multijournals.org/index.php/excellencia-imje/article/view/125>

DB, MF, DL, RR, AE., 2024